

SIMPLIFIED ROLLING CALCULATIONS: PART 3 THE COUPLING OF DEGREES OF FREEDOMS

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ABSTRACT

This paper is the third installment in the series dealing with the rolling motion (and other motions). This paper deals with the coupling between the degree of freedoms in general and specifically the interaction between the roll with other motions. This paper attempts to clean the added mass concept(s) from the detrimental errors that are currently used in the establishment implementation and put the theory in the science realm.

One of main fallacies that plagues the marine engineering is the added mass/moment of inertia implementation such as the famous fixed 6×6 matrix showing the added mass components. This implementation forces a special and strange anomaly equation or view on how added mass should be used. For strange reasons, this implementation was adapted by the establishment without any real questions or challenges. The consequences of this added mass implementation are non logical and counter to the physics that it is known today. For example, the acceleration in one direction causes angular acceleration in another DOF which is not really observed or does not make any sense. Furthermore, this implementation also leads to conceptual inability to reduce the degree of freedom in the model. Where these “coupling” effects (added mass coefficients) go when the number of DOF was reduced? Does this implementation violate the physics laws? To answer this question, this analysis suggests Something is terribly wrong with the common implementation and it violates Newton’s second law. One of main fallacies that plagues the marine engineering is the added mass/moment of inertia implementation such as the famous fixed 6×6 matrix showing the added mass components. This implementation forces a special and strange anomaly equations or view on how added mass should be used. For strange reasons, this implementation

was adapted by the establishment without any real questions or challenges. The consequences of this added mass implementation are non logical and counter to the physics that it is known today. For example, the acceleration in one direction causes angular acceleration in another DOF which is not really observed or does not make any sense. Furthermore, this implementation also leads to conceptual inability to reduce the degree of freedom in the model. Where do these “coupling” effects (added mass coefficients) go when the number of DOF is reduced? Does this implementation violate the physics laws? To answer this question, this analysis suggests something is terribly wrong with the common implementation and it violates Newton’s second law.

Here, the belief (in the standard implementation which is used by the vast majority of the industry if not all) is challenged. It was shown that this implementation can not stand any real scrutiny. It was shown that the added mass has only one whole value for the linear acceleration which can be broken into added mass different components in a different coordinate. The common implementation fails to explain the change of the added mass and other effects such as geometry effects. For example, sway does not affect the surge as opposed to the establishment implementation while the pitch and heave affect each other.

This analysis focuses on the relationship of added mass/added moment of inertia components based on the physical reasoning rather than the non realistic assumption and amorphous mathematical reasoning. It is explained that the connection between DOFs has three categories which are none, single or both relationships. The none means that the two movements (DOFs) do not affect each other (living in isolation). The single meaning is that one movement affects others but not the reverse. The both means that both movements affect each other. Thus, if one

wants to move from a fancy realm to a real world one and should abandon the establishment approach.

r right
 xx Around the x coordinate

NOMENCLATURE

Points of Interest

- $\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{A}', \mathcal{A}''$ Pivot point at the liquid level
- b Width of the body
- \bar{b} The ratio of b_1/b_2
- \mathcal{B} Buoyancy centroid
- \mathcal{G} Mass centroid
- \mathcal{K} Keel
- \mathcal{M} Metacenter none existent and imaginary point
- \emptyset Point on vertical after input angle
- \mathcal{Z} A point on \mathcal{GM} perpendicular to \mathcal{B}
- Λ A point on the liquid line crossing the counter left side
- χ A point on the liquid line crossing the counter rightsize

Variables

- a trapezoid dimension Coefficient
- b trapezoid dimension Coefficient
- c trapezoid dimension Coefficient
- D Total Ship (body) height
- \mathcal{D} New distance $\mathcal{B}'\emptyset$
- d Ship draft
- g Gravity constant
- I Moment of inertia either body or liquid
- \mathcal{L} Lagrangian
- L Angular momentum
- m Mass
- s Ship Length
- t Time
- \mathcal{T} Kinetic energy
- \mathcal{U} Potential energy
- w Ship weight
- \mathcal{X} Horizontal distance to the original pivot point
- x Distance in straight (movement) direction
- y Distance perpendicular to x

Greek Letters

- α Absolute value of difference angle right to left
- β Triangle letter as α sometimes
- ω Angular velocity
- ϕ Angle based on pivot at \mathcal{G} (commonly undefined)
- ρ Density
- θ Input Angle
- ξ The angle $\angle \mathcal{AKA}'$

Subscripts

- 0 Old location
- 1 Triangle 1
- 2 Triangle 2
- add, a Added mass/force
- b Floating body (ship)
- ℓ left

Key Words

Ship Rolling, Added Mass, Degree of Freedom, Changing of Moment of Inertia, Transfer Properties

1 Introduction

It can be argued that marine engineering (architecture) is the oldest engineering field. This field had several landmark breakthroughs like Archimedes (floating, and density) and Bouguer (buoyancy centroid movements) Darwin & Bessel (added mass) and this servant (Pivot points, Added Mass & Transfer properties). The added mass mass is important as it discussed by many fluid solid interaction such as Lefrancois (2017) utilizing this erroneous concept or Monterrubio find a way to calculate these non existent coefficients (2012). Several major fallacies entrenched into the field such pivot points in metacenter or later in mass centroid or somewhere undefined in between these two points (Bar-Meir 2023d; Bar-Meir 2023c; Bar-Meir 2023b; Bar-Meir 2023a), need to be extinguished. This paper dispels (or as some individuals will believe that it just attempts to dispel, wonder why?) several of the major issues, such as the control of the governing equations namely the added mass matrix. First, the history of the added mass is presented with the definitions of the coordinate system for this discussion. Later, the description of the examples on how the belief lead to strange situations in which contradicts the known physics laws. Followed by a discussion on the assumptions on which the added mass matrix is build and on what is wrong with these assumptions. The core is concluded with the actual effects of the degree of freedom the others.

The first installment of this series (Bar-Meir 2023e) briefly discussed the history in the belief in the pivot point locations of the ship industry and the violations the second law. In the second installment the horizontal movement of the pivot point during the rolling period was mentioned or discussed. Both these installments show the errors in the establishment's theory, first required change from the belief in the \mathcal{GM} to \mathcal{AG} and second: the effects of the abrupt and continuous contours on period. This installment deals with the coupling or connection among the various "degree of freedoms" or movements. The fourth installment will be dealing with the change of the pivot point due to the heave movement (up and down) and such. The fifth installment deals with the parallel transfer theorem for the added moment of inertia. The comprehensive study of the transfer properties hopefully will appear in a differ-

ent series (a very large job for one individual) hopefully soon. All this work is a draft to be summarized in the stability book (Bar-Meir 2022e).

Seeing the terrible errors produced in this field which derailed the research for hundreds of years suggest one to be humble. Thus, even with the excitement and pride of all these discoveries of changing almost whole undersigning, it hope no new major errors are introduced to replace the old ones. This author see himself as someone who is cable of making mistakes. If one find a mistake or more, please challenge this work.

2 History of the Added Mass

The “ancient” history of the added mass seems to be quite known and very minimal description is provided here. However, the implementation related to the marine industry is emphasized. The added mass was realized by the Darwin and Bessel etc because the need to measure the time precisely. The pendulum was used to measure the time. Thus knowing the added mass increase the accuracy. The added mass concept was in used by various scientists such as biologists for before it enters into the marine engineering. Lewis (1929) advocated for the use of the added mass because the additional mass affects the ship vibration (rolling). In any case, Lewis references Lamb (1879) and use the total energy in fluid filed interestingly with same notation of $2T$. No real progress was made in the understanding or the modeling of the added mass until 1963. For example, check the book by McGoldrick (1960) which emphasis in the belief that the ship is just a gigantic pendulum and hence can be use analogy to predict the frequency (with just a hint of dimensional analysis!). Landweber (1963) under the contract with the USA government build a 3×3 matrix the added mass coefficients. Landweber started his derivation by claiming that there is m_{ij} where $i = 1, 2, 3$ the same for j thus the kinetic energy if fluid is

$$2T = \sum_{i,j=1}^3 m_{i,j} U_i^2 U_j^2 \quad (1)$$

where U_i are the independent velocities (surge, sway, heave) of the ship (body) in a certain direction and $m_{i,j}$ is the mass component (the i^{th} direction due to the j^{th} velocity). Lou Landweber did not realize the velocities are not independent! A huge mistakes that estimated value of this error is in the hundred billions of dollars in a worthless research and construction of less optimized ships. Based on previously done work by Lamb, Landweber utilized the Neumann problems (based on the logic of electricity) applying it to fluid mechanics. The idea is actually wrong and this idea will be dissected later on. Notice that Landweber was a

mathematician turned into physicist felt that the fluid mechanics does not have special quirks. The presentation of possible three arbitrary velocity potential simply has no legs in reality. At this stage, the source of the error seems to be established and thus the claim that the added mass is constant (see Landweber’s paper just after equation 3) who is responsible for this error. In fact, this claim was not really examined or challenged. Yet, this claim has derailed real science based research work for several generations since then¹ (Ferreiro 2024).

Due to the fact that the concept of the added mass was used by several different industries is hard to determine what element/“feature” was discovered and when. In fact, the added mass was used in aviation of insects and birds when they move in air (gases, low density ratio?). A landmark paper by Fitzgerald (1909) citing Lamb on calculation of added mass and continue to suggest using the form of $d(MU)/dt$ instead the $M(dU/dt)$. This important idea actually based on 10 years earlier paper by the same author in a conference (sometime in 1899) which this author does not able access to. This author was not aware of these sources before writing this paper (see the Acknowledgment). The analysis was a bit simplistic but capture the main elements. It is note worthy to point out that the added mass was calculated for moving wing in air (while reasonable issues of density ratio were not clarified in the paper. It was to indicate not that it is wrong, but was not discussed.). Somehow this important analysis did not make to the general crowd of marine engineering and was lost. It is strange that this excellent idea of variable added mass was ignored and replaced by erroneous, complex, and fixed added mass (components). A side remark, the added mass was studied (more used) also by geological system for example by Gilbert in (1914).

No serious work was found on the solid–liquid interactions consider for example the “important” Haskind and Riman (1946) attempts to study the pitch and heave movement of ships. Fitzgerald’s approach was abandoned by Haskind et al where they used the erroneous the constant added mass of the establishment. Haskind et al also assumed that the pitch and heave also are decoupled. This work seems to influence all the works that followed. Papers such as by Ursell (1949) written by mathematicians who did not consider physics to be the main center issue aspects. For example, for the up and down (heave) motion the added mass is assumed to be constant which leads to no effect of the depth and the added mass is a step function. Notice this work contradicts von Karman (1929) idea where von Karman use technique similar to strip theory technique (variable added mass) and von Karman was not aware of Fitzgerald’s work and both assumed that added mass is variable (this topic was rediscovered at least four times if not more). The von Karman and

¹It paper escaped this author and broad into his view by Larrie Ferreiro see the acknowledgment.

Fitzgerald's idea of variable added mass were ignored. Motora (1959) continued the erroneous work of Ursell, and measured the ship added mass based on the assumption of constant value and that the ship creates a regular pendulum thus his experimental value are meaningless. The combination of pitch and heave for (Korvin-Kroukovsky and Jacobs 1957) is another work that impose the "physics" on the reality. For example, ignoring added mass for the heave motion and assuming or canceling the coupling between the pitch and heave.

The google scholar search of the added mass matrix shows about 6,440 results mostly related in some ways to the actual added mass matrix. In this section describes some of strange things that are observed/written (mostly recent) on this topic. Abbasi et al study the propeller (Abbasi, Asif, Kleinsorge, and Kistner 2024) and present work that utilize the 2×2 matrix. According to Abbasi et al there are only two DOFs or motions surge-roll (normally numerated 1 and 4). It is clear that the authors assumed that only two motions affect the propeller. The question is it justified according the establishment's theory? The propeller is mechanically restricted by being tied to the ship which is assumed to be a "infinity" mass. According, to this logic there should not be a surge movement as the propeller is tied to the ship as there should not be sway. Yet, here where it is getting interesting, using the m_{14} suggests that according to Abbasi et al the propeller moves relative to the ship which is absolute nonsense. Under the same arguments one can argue the same for the pitch. Notice here that the pivot point of the propeller is indeed at the center were the shaft is located. Yet, what here not mentioned is a remark on what should be used as the added mass and mass? It should be the ship's mass and added mass.

The work of Maki et al (2024) that study parametrically forced systems with application to ship rolling. What is interesting in this lack of serious literature review. Starting with the undefined variables in paper, such rotation angle, and thus also angular velocity (no definition of pivot point) whether or not if the pivot point is fix or not. Even these previous papers show lack of physics understanding as the authors only consider mathematical problem. For example, there is added mass, there is no full derivative of momentum, no change of added mass etc. The author suggested that artificially separation of the angel to two: the angle θ and angular velocity $\dot{\theta}$, is best mathematical technique. It seems that first getting the physics should be first priority. It will be well advised if the authors will carry real literature review.

Another strange article, Levy et al (1975) were suggesting a minimum of a function (not clear what that function really represents) provide added mass coefficients. This paper is interesting because the author started to use finite elements numerical technique and struggle to come out with a reasonable way to calculate the numerical values. While the physics is total mess up the considerable efforts are impressive.

This study of the history is not conclusive as there are

missing information for example, who first claimed or "prove" that $m_{ij} = m_{ji}$. While Apostolos Papanikolaou (2024) pointed out that the relationship "only holds for ZERO SPEED, not for ships with a forward speed!" This author (Bar-Meir 2023d) also show that this relationship also does not hold if the ship is not completely surrounded by infinite liquid which means for practical purposes that never happened. Initially, it was found in a textbook by Newman (2018) showing this proof (but according to M. Triantafyllou (2024) it appeared earlier). A search in library suggest that (Yih 1969) "showed" that added mass is symmetrical which indicate the $m_{ij} = m_{ji}$. This point is not conclusive as one expect something earlier might appear (between 1963-1969).

Additional point that has to be addressed is the negative added mass coefficients. For example, Mciver (1984) alleged that due to the surface tension and etc there are negative values. This idea is supported by the establishment for example McIver and McIver (2015) alleged that according to establishment's theory there are some zoons where the added mass are negative while in others the values are positive (assuming that zero is in between). The negative value is because the added mass is negative but because conceptual error in the added mass matrix. While McIver et al do not know what is the meaning of negative added mass or negative mass, they look at this topic assuming the establishment theory is correct. Added mass is due to the ideal flow concept not viscosity, or surface tension etc. So what is the negative added mass mean? The added (not subtracted) mass is the additional mass the body needs to pushes in order to move in the fluid. According to the establishment, the negative added mass is obtained in the derivations because the velocity is the opposite direction? Or something strange occurs due to the assumptions which steer the mathematics to produces negative added mass coefficients. This negative non existent coefficient(s) means that if the velocities components are considered independent, negative values can occur. This idea conflict with the added mass or mass in general.

Just to clarify this point, the actual added mass is in the direction of the body acceleration. Even in scenario where the accelerations is the opposite direction of the coordinate system, say $-x$ for example. That means the force is in the same direction as the acceleration and the added mass is still must be positive. In fact, this author cannot find scenario where added mass can be negative conceptually or with any mathematical manipulation. Remember the definition of mass (real physics) is resistance of the body to acceleration. If indeed there was negative mass it will violate the second law of thermodynamics. Note this case is normal and not what some people claim supper liquid where they claim to have negative mass.

The study of two spheres changing the volume was done by Felderhof (2024). One what expect this author to do a minimum literature review before publishing his paper. It is not clear how the fact that the cylinders are pulsing which should stare right into author face. Is the added mass not not function of the cylinder radius? This paper was published in arXiv an-

other mechanism where the establishment mechanism prevents free thinkers like this author to publish papers. Again the author claims that there are mass coefficients which affects each other spheres. Even as 2024 writing when writing this paper there who believe that in coefficients and compare methods which are false like Jahanbakhsh et al (2024). Fruncillo (2024) study the influence of the modeling of air planes and stability. This work seems to beyond the stretching of the reality that already beyond erroneous. Another example where imaginary realm live is Anargyros (2024) study the submarine under near the water surface. While claims that the heave does not effect the roll or the pitch. Yet, the pitch should affect the surge and sway etc. Mandru et al (Mandru, Rusu, Bekhit, and Pacuraru 2024) study the added resistance. Before comment on the errors in the paper how one conclude that global climate change is real? Any way, using the full equation like Fitzgerald make paper real not neglecting the main contribution.

3 Definition and Coordinate System

FIGURE 1. A schematic to explain the ship motion names.

Generally, the coordinate system requires directions and an origin. For complex operations like ship movements etc typical names have been adapted and several different coordinate systems were in use. The typical names of the ship motions are described in fig. 1. The velocities divided into two categories linear and rotational. For the linear velocities, the origin of the coordinate system is not important only the orientation. In a traditional approach the narrowest dimension determines one of direction and the gravity determines the second coordinate and thus also the third coordinate (most of the time, the right hand convention is adapted). From a physical point of view, the narrowest dimension is also typically the least resistance part of the body. For general body, if there is no preference, the coordinate can be based on the gravity only and arbitrary in the other directions.

The velocity along the narrowest direction, typically refers as x and the averaged velocity is the ship velocity and the deviation from this velocity is called the surge. The other two velocities are called sway (side to side) and the up and down is

heave. While the ship or floating body have three different velocities components in reality the ship has only one velocity. In other word, when discussing the different components it has to remember that these velocity components are part of the actual **single** total velocity. To some extend, one can talk about these components separately in the sense of changing the velocity due to the change of the frame of reference. For example, when the body has sway velocity, the frame of reference can change and move with the sway (specially when it has a constant velocity) hence in this frame of reference, the surge velocity is not affected by sway or even heave.

The rotational degree of freedoms are harder to define as the rotation pivot point (line) has to be determined first. For rsymmetrical (Bar-Meir 2024b) body the pivot point is relatively simple as it is at the liquid line (surface) for (middle of the liquid line) rolling and pitching. Even though the ship is not rsymmetrical for the pitch this part can be roughly considered as rsymmetrical especially for large ships. For the yaw, the added mass centroid has to be calculated to find the pivot point (Bar-Meir 2023d). The intersection of the roll pivot line with the pitch pivot line (both at the liquid surface) is the prefer location for the origin. Only when the pivot points (lines) are calculated or determined, the origin of the coordinate system is established. Note that the yaw pivot point might not be at the origin. The complicated cases of bodies that are unrsymmetrical which have moving horizontal pivot point (Bar-Meir 2024b) the origin can be assumed to be initially either as for the rsymmetrical bodies (the initial stability point). The origin can move to the new pivot point or stay at the initial point but taking into account the moving of the pivot point. This complication requires modification of Triantafyllou's derivation (2003, chapter 1) which hopefully will done be in stability book.

4 Establishment Model Conflicts

The question is about how false or erroneous establishment's theories which are currently the mainstream and only accepted theories that everyone compelled to use. This situation is like a fantasy taken out straight out Hollywood or Bollywood movies where only one individual fight these evil forces. A polite man (Landweber) who paid honestly by the USA government to write a new theory and creates non existent physical situations. No one has challenge this ridicules idea or at least examine its validity. Furthermore, this strange situation aggravated by the "scientists" (Faltinsen etc) who added additional errors such as three rotational motions without defining the pivot points. Now, since these anomalies really do not work, new experimental work had to be carried out and strange explanations have to be created to explain conflicts with reality. As it will be shown below, Newton's laws do not "work" with these theories and no one consider that to be wrong. Then, when an outsider points out these terrible errors, the establishment sends minions like Mathias Marley

from Norwegian University of Science and Technology to curse this author. Everyone has probably read this story before, it is called the emperor's new clothes story (perhaps minus the evil intentions). What will be the end of current story? Why no one realized that this theory is simply rubbish.

4.1 Fixed Coefficients Conflicts

Without going through the derivations of the governing equation, several observations can be made. First, according to establishment's theory there is no global added mass even for the original linear 3×3 matrix only components (linear acceleration components). According to all (almost) the works in this area, these components are constant associated with a specific ship or floating body. According to this idea, an arbitrary body can have all the added components (non zero mostly and probably positive). Thus, this allegation (or model by "scientists" like Faltinsen) means that the body has three accelerations (forces) existing once there is any acceleration in any direction (for the Landweber's original idea). In other words, if one acceleration exists then the other two accelerations must exist as well. One can observe this claim from the equations or from the way the equations were constructed (three independent velocity components). However, when one pushes (force) in the trajectory through mass centroid of the boat or the floating body, the body will move in the direction of the force and not in any other direction (not even rotation).

As if this routine observed fact stand against this anomaly face is not enough, consider the following situation. A body under a surge acceleration with a positive added mass coefficient will force an acceleration upward (downward). While one can allege that the energy to raise the body is supplied by the force (how? Who knows? Remember it is ideal fluid). There is another small pesky thing: momentum. Beside the fact that this phenomenon never have been observed, it requires a considerable flow downward to keep momentum in z in balance! Any control volume shows that liquid has flow downward. How does this large jet downward works with the conservation of momentum and mass and keep the water level at the same height. It simply is not possible. Just draw a control volume around the boat in fig. 2 to show that it simply cannot work.

FIGURE 2. The original force in the surge direction result in acceleration (force) in heave direction according to the establishment's model.

Evading the calculation of the total added mass is one of the major flaw in the logic of the calculations of any parameter dealing with the movement of floating body (generally also for moving body in liquid). In fact, quite extensive literature review demonstrates that there is no work that calculated the actual (total) added mass or added moment of inertia. The canceling of the total added mass for start, imposes fixed mass coefficients and thus a fixed total added mass which contradicts the reality. This postulation of fixed added mass does not sit well with the change of the body origin, phase, geometrical change of the body contradict the observation and logic. It basically and implicitly states that the added mass of any rectangle is identical to added mass of any parallelogram with same area. Obviously, this idea is fundamentally and clearly false. But more than that, many marine creatures are using the change of the added mass to rotate and change direction and speed in critical survivable situations. Thus, looking at all (almost) the papers on marine that were published suggest that their usage of fix added mass is simply erroneous. Note there are those adapted the schizophrenic approach, for example (Paniccia, Graziani, Lugni, and Piva 2022), recognize the change in the added mass and yet ignore the effect on the governing equations. For this discussion, it is considered to be like elephant with wings.

The way information pass in science is normally (should) by publishing technical papers, conference papers, articles, and books in that order. Thus, these multi layers steps allow to filter out the nonsense and errors. This multi layers idea does not always work. The most obvious example is Landweber introduction of added mass matrix. These errors occur because no real literature review has been done. Further these errors even aggravated by a volunteer or more. For example, see Faltinsen and colleagues inserting equations even without proper definitions of the basic angle and hence it has destroyed generations engineers in process. This situation repeats itself even in a plain stability of prism uniform density body. Bouguer's theory is missing many details and not precise thus any use of theory has to be extremely careful. But more than that, compering the stability of sold body issue (buckling) to floating body is strange because the governing equation is different. Thompson (2023) conducted experiment on specific wood and specific geometry. Thompson's work, as writing this paper, is very recent. This example how an establishment's "scientist" from very establish university (University of Cambridge) is so clueless to what is going on and attach his name to this high school level paper with a fundamental error. Thompson's paper just promotes ignorance especially when claiming that it is a bifurcation solution.

4.2 Non Existing Coupling Conflicts

The main "feature" of the establishment idea is that the acceleration in one direction creates acceleration in different direction. This claim based on term of a_{ij} where a is the added mass com-

ponent. As writing this paper, the change of the notation from $m \rightarrow a$ seem to occur in 199x but was not pinpoint to any specific paper. Techet from MIT (2016) stated that

Quotations

Added mass forces can arise in one direction due to motion in a different direction, and thus we can end up with a 6×6 matrix of added mass coefficients.

While it is clearly absurd to assume that acceleration (force) in x causes acceleration in y , one can simply raise the question isn't this idea violates of the Newton's laws. Simply, the establishment's statement "well dummy you should believe us" see for example Techet's statement

Quotations

A good way to think of the added mass components, m_{ij} , is to think of each term as mass the j^{th} associated with a force on the body in the direction due to a unit acceleration in the j^{th} direction.

Consider the case where the non zero added mass coefficient ties the rotational DOF with a linear DOF (it does not matter which one). This coefficient according the establishment's theory is only function of the body geometry (there is no disagreement about this point, if the establishment's logic hold for these wrong assumptions.). A force is applied on the body in the direction of this DOF. There two possibilities one the force goes through the mass centroid (assumed that this point is clear) and the force is skew and miss the mass centroid. According to the standard physics understanding the force does not create torque but in the other case it does create torque. Here is an example the standard physics claims that in one case there will be rotation and anther there will be no rotation. As rotation requires a torque and without it there will not be a rotation. Yet, our beloved establishment's theory vehemently believes that it does not matter if the force trajectory aim at the centroid. To conform this idea check how the establishment's equations are set up. So on one hand the physics tell us that without torque no rotation and on the other hand, Faltinsen and etc claim that it does not matter. This idea conflicts with the basic physical principle is another strong indication that how wrong is the establishment's theory.

For example, consider Skejic and Faltinsen's work on submarine at periscope depth (2022) where coupled surge–sway–yaw are considered. The typical errors (the paper full of those) such wrong pivot point etc are ignored for this discussion. If the added mass matrix idea is accepted, it does not matter what the researchers want it or not, the added mass coefficients exist regardless (at least according to establishment's theory). Thus, the full 6×6 matrix exist because the added mass coefficients do not depend on the depth (well according to Faltinsen etc its own the-

ory). According to the establishment's theory,? the yaw acceleration (angular velocity) creates heave acceleration. These added mass coefficients are created because the body is not symmetrical and there must be according the establishment logic. Yet, these coefficients cannot be ignored just because the authors want them to vanish. In their analysis despite their "theory", they instinctively knew and realize that their theory is a pure garbage and therefore they ignore it. Thus, they were able to ignore the other 3 DOFs (roll, heave, pitch) in spite their own doctrine. The added mass component in the direction of the heave is non zero because the structure on top of the submarine. The same can be said to roll motion as well as the pitch motion. It is like Microsoft run Linux on their servers to host their websites.

The acceleration in the direction of DOF causes acceleration in another direction. This statement include rotation causes linear motion and linear motion causes rotation according to this logic. The idea that linear momentum can be created by angular momentum in ideal fluid is required by the establishment' theory. No place in the literature has shown that is possible or no shown any mechanism to achieve it. The physics of converting a vortex or circulation to a linear momentum requires some cooperation of the other side body or boundary. This idea should noted with issue of the force at the centroid and the skew force. This requirement cannot be fulfilled because the model suggested by the authors is a submarine which must be at certain depth. Furthermore, this idea mandates that the force acting on the body centroid causes angular momentum on the body. As stated in the class notes (Judge 2019; Techet 2005) for 1: Surge, 2: Sway, and 6: Yaw, the governing equations according to this idea are

$$F_1 = -m_{11} \frac{dU_1}{dt} + m_{12} \frac{dU_2}{dt} + m_{16} \frac{dU_6}{dt} \quad (2)$$

$$F_2 = -m_{21} \frac{dU_1}{dt} + m_{22} \frac{dU_2}{dt} + m_{26} \frac{dU_6}{dt} \quad (3)$$

$$F_6 = -m_{61} \frac{dU_1}{dt} + m_{62} \frac{dU_2}{dt} + m_{66} \frac{dU_6}{dt} \quad (4)$$

Where F_1 , F_2 , and F_6 , are the surge and sway forces and yaw torque respectively. The same is taught in USA navy academy see for example, (Judge 2019). These formulations are the common in the marine engineering as noted by Techet.

4.3 Coupling Conflicts With Physics

One should expect some physical reasoning for the coupling between the DOF and on some strange non existent mathematical functionality. According to the establishment's model, the sway affects the heave and heave affects the sway. Once the mass coefficients are determined they have a fix value and no additional information or understanding is needed. However, the physics begs to differ. As first approximation Brennen (1982) suggested that

the cross section of the shape provide an estimate of the added mass. Thus, according Brennen the added mass approximated linearly depended with cross section which is direct function of the heave. Hence, ship is moving up the sway added mass is reduced and the ship is moving down the added mass is increased. Totally the opposite to the establishment's theory. The same argument can be described the effect of the heave on the surge and other DOF. However, the sway does not affect the heave as oppose to the establishment's ideology especially when sway is in constant velocity. Simply,

The other DOF that affects the surge and sway is the yaw. The same can be said on the roll which effect several other motions. Beside the motion effects on the each other, there is a whole issues dealing with the change of the body like moving of the caudal fin. This change added mass and thus also change of pivot point etc (Bar-Meir 2022b; Bar-Meir 2022c; Bar-Meir 2022d). The establishment's theory does not have answer to the change of volume of the moving object like octopus.

5 The Corrections Of Derivations

Korotkin's book (2008) becomes closer to the go to book on added mass yet is full with fundamentals errors. These fundamentals errors will be explained utilizing the derivations provided in Korotkin's book. Korotkin discusses the added mass/added moment of inertia coefficients and presented the standard velocity potential for the rotational velocities which also appeared in Newman (2018). The aim in this section is to demonstrate that the establishment's approach is fundamentally erroneous in two respects one: independence of the velocity and two: rotation potential. It is assumed that the reader has access to Korotkin's book or Newman (2018) or one of the original papers that introduced these errors. Some efforts to present establishment's equations will be made. As a first step, the rotational potential in the establishment's model will be analyzed and the errors will be expo/sed because these errors are easiest explain. Later, the linear potential (Landweber) will be examined and the errors will be presented.

5.1 Rotational Potential

This part deals with the equations which normally counted 4, 5, and 6 and typically are named with motions (DOFs) as the roll, pitch, and yaw for historical (and some logical) reasons. The derivations normally start with the idea that the velocity as presented as a gradient of the potential function. Then, the potential function is manipulated using variety identities to obtain a certain presentation that show that the whole field depend solely on the velocity at body boundaries (and hopefully no other bodies in the field). As the velocity field is caused by the boundaries hence the velocity field replace by the boundaries which is the core idea of these identities. Thus, this technique must be precise in deter-

mining the surface velocities and hence the exact location of the pivot lines is essential especially when dealing with three dimensional situations.

The essence of the idea requires that there is a pivot point around which the body is rotating. The establishment's model assumes that this pivot point is at the body mass centroid. This idea was dispelled and it is erroneous (2023d), for floating body it is at middle of the liquid surface. Thus, the establishment's model as expressed by Korotkin equation (1.5) is not valid

$$U = U_0 + \vec{\omega} \times \vec{r} \quad (5)$$

where U is the velocity at the interface, U_0 is the velocity of the centroid, $\vec{\omega}$ instantaneous angular velocity (not really defined but assumed the pivot point is at body mass centroid), and \vec{r} is a vector to the body's surface from the body's mass centroid. Notice that $|\omega| \neq \sqrt{\omega_x^2 + \omega_y^2 + \omega_z^2}$ because none of angular velocity is at mass centroid. In writing this equation in this section, Korotkin's notation was used locally for this section only. In spite of the error (this error is actually self suggested in the definition which are angular velocity, and the angle), derivations will continue a bit. In other words, this error is the location of the pivot points. Furthermore, a question why is it when dealing the rotation the question, where is the pivot was not raised? Explicitly, writing the velocity components reads

$$\begin{aligned} U_x &= U_{0x} + \omega_y z - \omega_z y, \\ U_y &= U_{0y} + \omega_z x - \omega_x z, \\ U_z &= U_{0z} + \omega_x y - \omega_y x. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Again, it is very puzzling that the establishment's scientists (Faltinsen, Landweber, Judge, etc and even petty level like Song from S. Korea Inha University) did not asked if all the rotations are at the same pivot point. On the body contour, the velocity (only if all the rotations have the same point which not correct) is

$$U_n = U_x \cos(n,x) + U_y \cos(n,y) + U_z \cos(n,z). \quad (7)$$

where $\cos(n,x)$ is the projection x on tangent to the contour, as also this obviously apply to the other two coordinates. Equation (7) is a statement that no fluid is flowing through the body.

Substituting eq. (6) into eq. (7) reads

$$U_n = U_{0x} \cos(n, x) + U_{0y} \cos(n, y) + U_{0z} \cos(n, z) + \omega_x (y \cos(n, z) - z \cos(n, y)) + \omega_y (z \cos(n, x) - x \cos(n, z)) + \omega_z (x \cos(n, y) - y \cos(n, x)) \quad (8)$$

Equation (8) is based on the idea that the pivot is fixed and located at mass centroid. However, the pivot is not at the mass centroid and is not fixed (Bar-Meir 2024b) hence this derivation is simply wrong. Thus, the popular presentations by (Techet 2005; Judge 2019), and other publications and class notes that are simply and completely wrong and spoil the whole generation of marine professionals. This error knocked all the rotation potential and hence the added moment of inertia in all the works up to this point. For practical purposes, all the works that dealt with the rotation in marine including all the MMG models are simply erroneous.

The linearity of the motion according to common “experts” can at most be represented as

$$\varphi = U_{0x} \varphi_1 + U_{0y} \varphi_2 + U_{0z} \varphi_3 + \omega_x \varphi_4 + \omega_y \varphi_5 + \omega_z \varphi_6 \quad (9)$$

Is the situation defined by the equations are just an attempt to describe the physics. The answer is clear, if one believe in 6×6 matrix then all works that were used 3×3 are simply wrong. If one believes in the way that is present in the last 60 years or more then not used the right pivot point means that the solutions are wrong or erroneous. Now what left to do is the prove that the linear potential is also erroneous which will be discussed in the next section.

5.2 Linear Potential

The presentation of eq. (9) is arbitrary as if there no connection between the velocity components. If this idea is accepted then strange things happened where acceleration in x causes force in y . While this presentation is accepted by all those who accepted the idea of added mass, clearly, this idea must be challenged. Especially when the development grows into further ridicules work like (Song, Kim, and Dai 2024) calculation/using GM with wrong equation. More information about that paper in (Bar-Meir 2024a). There is, as opposed to previous discussion, emphasis on the errors in the equations.

There are at least two tactical approaches to show that the equations and hence 3×3 matrix to be wrong. The first approach is change of coordinates and second to argue and present the errors in the equations derivations. First the coordinates can be reoriented such that the coordinate system point into the body velocity. In that case, clearly, there is only a single velocity compo-

nent. Since the velocity of the body has only one component the conclusion is that there is only one element of the added mass. Equation (9) simply reduced into a simple one term function as

$$\varphi = U_0 \varphi \quad (10)$$

In that case, the kinetic energy of the field can be written after the standard manipulation as

$$T = -\frac{\rho}{2} \iint_S \varphi \frac{d\varphi}{dn} dS \quad (11)$$

where φ is the velocity potential and the derivative of the velocity is with respect to the body direction. Notice in this case if you have only one component then the energy is simply related to a sole component. Thus, the establishment’s approach is simply wrong.

The result, intuitively expected, is that the floating body causes all velocities in the field. This result is oppose to common approach which belief that there are six (now only three) independent sources of velocities. However, as the derivation started with the velocity components ended with sole but whole velocity has only one element. In that case clearly there is no matrix of 6×6 (now only 3×3). The couplings are left into the terms inside the equation rather the artificial coordinate system dependency. Derivations that depend on the coordinate system should be coordinate system independent mean that something is fundamentally wrong.

The alternative reasoning does not utilize the coordinate system change but looking the standard derivations. In arbitrary system the ship or body has three different velocity components which are orthogonal to each other. The energy of the system is related to U^2 . Thus, according to the Pythagorean theorem when adding two or more squire terms like $U_x^2 + U_y^2 + U_z^2 = U^2$. Hence, again the velocity components are actually the velocity and they cannot be separated for energy calculations.

6 Actual Connection between the DOFs

This section offers a discussion on the connection between various degree of freedoms. The common approach believes in the connections based on the added mass components which are influencing each other regardless to the physics forcing and giving birth to the non realistic and mysterious ties. In fact, these establishment’s connections violated physics laws. For example, according the Faltinsen and colleagues, the surge affects the sway and sway affects the surge. In this paper, the opposite approach is taken. For specific example, the body moves in a surge (forward) and moving sway (side to side) when both movements are totally independent. As observer moves with the floating body

sway will “see” the same equations as stationary observer which is correct also for surge. Notice, these statements are applied only to ideal flow.

So how the coupling or connections between the DOFs really created or work? The first mechanism is when a movement (DOF) in one direction change the geometry (orientation, shape) in another direction. For example, a heave (up and down) changes the geometry of the floating body that sway movement “see”. The second mechanism is the change of orientation such as a roll changes the cross section of floating body from a rectangular to a different such as trapezoid. The third mechanism is the change of the linear momentum direction such as yaw changes some of the momentum surface movements (sway and surge). In fig. 3 depicts a boat that undergoes yaw DOF. In that case, if the coordinate system is fix with the boat then the momentum is reduced or in alternative the coordinate system is fixed then then shape of the boat changes and those the added mass is affected.

FIGURE 3. An exaggerated schematic to explain the yaw DOF effect.

Generally, the governing equation in a vectors form in some situations in claim liquid can be written as

$$\frac{D((m_a + m_b)\vec{U})}{Dt} + \underbrace{B_1 \vec{U}}_{\text{first kind resistance}} + \underbrace{B_2 \vec{U}^2}_{\text{second kind resistance}} + \underbrace{\square \mathbf{AG}}_{\text{righting arm}} = 0 \quad (12)$$

This strange equation eq. (12) is actually typical equation for simplified situations where \square is some kind function related to righting arm (\mathbf{AG}) which can very complicate. At this stage, this function is left in a very generic form. It can be noticed that derivative is not d and D which in fluid standard also include the convective element (Bar-Meir 2022a). Also note that while the added mass is not a vector it has different valve depending on the orientation (Bar-Meir 2022e, ver 0.8.5a and above).

The derivative of the momentum yield many derivatives which include change of direction, change of magnitude of the velocity and added mass (moment of inertia). The coupling term

which is part of the momentum change and expressed as

$$\text{coupling term} = \vec{U} \left(\overbrace{\frac{D(m_a)}{Dt}}^{\text{volume}} + \overbrace{\frac{D(m_a)}{Dt}}^{\text{orientation}} + \overbrace{\frac{D(m_a)}{Dt}}^{\text{phase}} + \overbrace{\frac{D(m_a)}{Dt}}^{\text{geometry}} + \overbrace{\frac{D(m_a)}{Dt}}^{\text{pivot}} + \overbrace{\frac{D(m_b)}{Dt}}^{\text{pivot}} + \overbrace{\frac{D(m_b)}{Dt}}^{\text{organic}} \right) \quad (13)$$

The change of added moment of inertia of the body was discussed in (Bar-Meir 2024b). The first derivative of the added mass has many components which are the way the DOFs connecting the different equations. The first term in this list the volume have example such as (Weymouth and Triantafyllou 2012; Weymouth and Triantafyllou 2013). The second term deals with changing the orientation of the body relative to the main movement. The third term deals with phase change which is very large topic for surface (floating bodies) vehicle. This term normally deals with rsymmetrical and unrsymmetrical bodies and it predicted that this topic will be researched for many years to come. The geometry term will be dealing with biological or marine creature where the body change. The first paper on pivot point was done by this author (2024b) and will G-d help will presented in the next installment. The next two terms deal mostly with marine and aviation biological creature and it complementary to the added terms. An example will be provided in the next installment for the vertical pivot point. Here only a discussion on the generality is offered.

The way one degree of freedom affects another is by changing the shape (orientation) of the ship (body). The DOFs that totally independent are the sway and surge as they do no change the geometry the other DOFs. It has to point out there categories in connections one is totally independent, two one way connection, and three two ways connections. The connection depends on both degree of freedoms. The case of sway–surge is first category: the independent. An example of one way connections is sway (side to side) with the roll (rotation around the long dimension). Clearly the sway does not affects the rolling as the rolling equations are identical with or without sway but roll affects the sway as the body shape is different geometry for roll movement which creates a different added mass thus affects the sway. The case of roll–heave (up and down) is the category where both degree of freedoms affects each others. When the body is the heaving geometry of submerged part of body change and hence affect the roll. And the opposite is also correct, the roll change geometry the heave movement “sees” as the orientation change and hence the added mass is changed. There are 18 combinations of degree of freedoms and only 9 are unique. The most “docile” is sway and surge and the all the rotations are very

aggressive/interactive and the most aggressive is roll. The interactions are summarized in table 1. Notice that left column shows the bottom 4 are the active DOFs when combined with with the first row also the last 4 are the active one.

TABLE 1. Coupling Effects Among The DOFs None: isolation, Single: One way, Double: two ways

	surge	sway	yaw	heave	roll	pitch
surge	0	0	1	1	1	1
sway	0	0	1	1	1	1
yaw	1	1	0	2	2	2
heave	1	1	2	0	2	2
roll	1	1	2	2	0	2
pitch	1	1	2	2	2	0

7 Summary

This paper that started due to the cursing letters received from several minions who strongly felt the need to insult this author so that they feel good about their erroneous work. Since they claimed this author did produce new material and if there is new material it must be erroneous (see for example, Mathias Marley some of explanations). One assume that it comes with territory and that is okay. In the explanation of these concepts (in this paper) it become clear that they should be present to the general public so this author does not have to repeat itself. The same can be said to the transfer properties papers it looks clear to this author but some do see as clear.

The establishment’s governing equation contains the mass matrix as the main part. This paper change and correct the governing. In doing so this paper changes the course of the research in navigation from nonsense to science. Now, it is clear that there is no added mass matrix and the mixed coefficients don’t exist. For example check the contrast between the establishment idea and this author’s theory. A horizontal floating perfect cylinder going up and down (heave DOF) with sway has no added mass coefficients beside m_{11} and m_{22} because the symmetry. Yet, in actually this perfect cylinder during the heave change the added mass and hence effect the sway motion. So, the establishment’s theory is wrong violates the Newton’s second law and opposite reactions to the what really happening.

Now, why this error occur and who are responsible for worthless, useless, and erroneous research have been reported. According google reports that are several individuals with over 50k citations most if not all erroneous. It is shame that these errors went so far to this point.

In the next paper, a more explicit discussion the connection or coupling. Nevertheless, here the connection has been shown how the coupling these DOFs are to do with physical phenomena was provided. The table summarized the connections of the coupling between the various DOFs. In a way, the real relations are shown and when the path when the some DOF can be compromised was layout generally.

Prediction

It is not very common to write an article that basically revolutionized the whole field by changing the governing equations. This author has already done one revolution in die casting where he changed the whole field upside one. The question that raise how long it will take to change the majority to field to used the correct technology. In die casting it took about 35 years where the establishment basically had major controlled the publishing avenues. Initially in the process and as results of conflict this author faced many obstacles. Later the main location (Ohio State University) seems to be melting away because the shame of the trashy research work that done by the main faculty because all was exposed.

The question how long it will take to adapt the improved and correct governing equations (new technology). There are those who publicly put their head in the sand such as Faltinsen, Fossen, and Carlos Guedes Soares, and Skjetne and several Korean and Japanese researchers. While in die casting this stage disappeared very fast, here in a large field like marine engineering this will take longer. For one, the research grants in die casting are only less on 1% as compared to marine engineering which is about 5 billions dollars. They will be able to produce erroneous research for much longer. With the forgoing it seems even with how fast information pass today the process seem to take about 10 years. It will be interesting if this prediction will turn out to be reasonably correct.

Disputation

After the minion Mathias Mathias from Norwegian University of Science and Technology and probably his masters (it hard to believe graduate student done it by himself) claiming that either all was known or if it was not known it must be wrong, here is a challenge for this minion and his masters and the other minions. Additionally there are those quietly belief in these claims without advertise their belief. Furthermore, there are those who put the horse blindfold to minimize their exposure the new technology like Carolyn Q. Judge so they will not realize their work was useless/wrong. With about five billion dollars a year in research grants and producing research papers that violate the second law of thermodynamics it is time to examine these claims. This author is calling for disputation since the subject is science and true

matter. If you believe in one or more of the topics below you have an invitation for disputation.

These topics are

1. The pivot point of the rolling or pitching is either in the metacenter or mass centroid or “rolling center” or “somewhere between the metacenter and gravity centroid”. The rolling center mentioned in this paper.
2. If you believe that there are really added mass matrix. In other words, if you believe that there are m_{ji} (a_{ij}).
3. The moment of inertia is independent of the pivot point.
4. Added mass or the added moment of inertia is constant. As the governing equations as defined in Fossen or MIT or Caroline Judge’s classes.
5. The pivot point is constant in the ship navigation equations.
6. If you believe that MMG equations are correct or logical or sensible.
7. If you believe the strip theory as is described or is correct as in MIT’s classes .
8. If you believe that added mass is not actually a single added mass (a core belief in the common establishment’s doctrine).
9. If you believe that more 20% of the world research in the ship stability/navigation does not violate the second law of thermodynamics or Newton’s second law.
10. \mathcal{GM} is the correct righting arm of the ship.

Acknowledgment

This paper describe a progress in this kind of magnitude has some willing and unwilling partners. First, thank you for Naomi Marshak who corrected the English of early draft of the first 6 pages which her questions added more material. No one can clean all the English errors that this authors capable to produce, Second, the unwilling participants such as Carolyn Q. Judge from USNA that set to “protect” her students from the truth. Mathias Marley his lack of understating and willingness to curse this author brought this paper. At least as opposed to the other minions who demand to remain anonymous, he was willing to show his name. The treasure trove that Larrie Ferreiro gave is so large that at one point this author was contemplating making him as co-author. Also great thanks to Apostolos Papanikolaou who provide significant information about the logic of the progression. Thank you to Michael Triantafyllou who was courteous to provide information on the added matrix symmetry. He was part of the group which discover the added mass change due to the change of volume (see ref) before this author (yes, there is an arm race who discover first). Discovery order, 1) Fitzgerald, 2) Lautrup, 3) von Karman, 4) Weymouth and Triantafyllou (others), and 5) This author. Notice while all independent the elements they discovered are different.

As example of fad’s believer Dr. Song provided inspiration on how one can double down on stupidity is so amusing. Some

discussion elements on parallel theorem remained and persist in this paper please ignore those. There are those to contribute via discussions but asked to remain anonymous, thank you! Also thank you to Kostas Spyrou by his plagiarizing demonstrated how the establishment deals with the “rogue agent” by netscaping his/their material.

About the Author

As opposed to many other researchers, this author does not brag about how many citations his work has or jobs he held but only points to how many breakthroughs he has made and on how many people plagiarized his work. In the die casting industry, he has revolutionized the field by solving several major open questions. These questions include the critical plunger velocity, pQ^2 diagram, intensification pressure and critical vent area etc (for those who not familiar with die casting, these are the main pliers of die casting.). It has to be mentioned that the die casting establishment believed in solutions which violated the second law of the thermo and has spent millions promoting these beliefs (like the woke religion). Since the problems were not solved, literally hundreds of CFD teams from all over the world attempted to solve the problem in vain where this author solved them. The establishment fought against publishing these discoveries. The irony is that these author’s models today are undisputed and accepted in the industry.

Furthermore, this servant solved several open problems in shock dynamics and potential of compressed substances. Additionally, this author solved the deep ocean pressure and speed of sound which many oceanographers failed to calculate (Pushka Equation).

Bar–Meir was instrumental in developments of the added mass (properties) concepts. He has differentiated between the added properties and the transfer properties. He discovered the change of the added mass and its effects on the governing equations. He invented the stability dome for floating bodies and in the process developed the equation for centroid of circle segment.

Kostas J. Spyrou, when he gave his keynote lecture, basically copied many concepts that were developed by Bar–Meir (such as the stability dome) and presented them as his ideas. These concepts had never appeared in the literature before. It is interesting to point out that Dr. Spyrou has been observed downloading Bar–Meir’s book. Dr. Spyrou’s behavior is not unique to him only. Dr. Kenneth Brezinsky went out of his way to declare that Bar–Meir’s calculations of compressible gas potential were useless and baseless. However, Brian J. Cantwell from Stanford University recently decided to copy Bar–Meir’s idea and to dedicate a whole section (2.9) to it in his book (and probably also in his classes) to this idea. Except that Dr. Cantwell oversimplified the idea (he removed the dimensionless presentation), maybe because he did not fully understand it. The ship stability went major revision and basically revamped the field in particular the

added mass (properties). The old governing equations yielding hundreds percent errors had to be modified due to discoveries of this author.

Conflict of Interest

The author Genick Bar–Meir certify that he has NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity or person with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers’ bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent–licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials or individuals discussed in this manuscript.

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